

Pedagogical Opportunities For Improving Students' Musical Skills**Ilyosjon Ro'zimurodov Azamatovich**

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the pedagogical possibilities of improving the skills of musical performance in students studying in higher educational institutions from a scientific, theoretical and practical point of view. The study highlights the role of modern pedagogical approaches, interactive methods, and individual and differentiated education principles in increasing the musical and creative activity of students in the process of musical performance, forming technical and artistic performance skills.

Keywords: musical education, pedagogical opportunities, performance skills, professional competence, interactive methods, individual approach, creative activity, music pedagogy.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and modernization of the educational process, the content and quality of musical education in the higher education system are being revised based on new pedagogical approaches. In particular, the issue of forming and improving the skills of musical performance in students is emerging as one of the priority areas of music education. Because instrumental performance is an important factor in developing not only technical skills, but also the student's musical thinking, aesthetic taste, creative imagination, and professional self-awareness.

Being limited to traditional teaching methods in the educational process does not fully meet the needs and capabilities of today's student. Modern pedagogy requires the introduction of educational technologies aimed at developing the student's personal experience, individual performance style, and independent creative activity. From this perspective, the use of interactive methods, differential, and person-oriented approaches in instrumental performance classes allows for the effective development of performance skills.

The process of instrumental performance is also important in forming the student's stage culture, emotional stability, and creative freedom. In this process, the teacher's professional skills, methodological training, and creative approach directly affect the quality of the student's performance. Pedagogically properly organized classes help students realize their own capabilities, overcome difficulties in performance, and develop the skills of independent work on themselves. Therefore, identifying pedagogical opportunities for improving students' instrumental

performance skills and effectively implementing them in educational practice is one of the urgent tasks facing music pedagogy. This issue is of significant theoretical and practical importance in organizing an educational process aimed at increasing the professional competence of future music specialists and harmoniously mastering national and world musical culture. The process of forming and developing instrumental performance skills is a complex, multifaceted pedagogical phenomenon, which is inextricably linked with the student's musical abilities, psychological state, and personal creative potential. The effectiveness of this process depends, first of all, on the correct definition of the content of education and the rational use of pedagogical opportunities. In music education, performance should be considered not only as a set of technical exercises, but also as a creative activity that reflects the student's inner musical experiences and artistic thinking.

In the educational process, an individual approach to improving students' instrumental performance skills is of particular importance. Since each student has different musical hearing, rhythmic intuition, and technical training levels, individualization of classes serves to improve the quality of performance. This requires the teacher to differentially organize the educational process and use methodological approaches aimed at gradually mastering complex performance elements.

The use of interactive methods in instrumental performance increases the student's activity and develops his creative independence. In the process of training, analyzing and comparing performance samples, expressing musical images, and organizing collective performance exercises expand the musical thinking of students. In particular, through ensemble and orchestral performance, students develop a culture of musical communication, listening, and mutual harmony skills. Another important aspect of pedagogical opportunities is the effective organization of students' independent performance activities. During independent training, the student acquires the skills of in-depth analysis of the work, overcoming technical difficulties, and self-control of the performance process. In this, the teacher's methodological instructions, performance plan, and tasks aimed at reflective analysis play an important role. Also, pedagogical conditions aimed at developing stage culture in instrumental performance training play an important role. Students' ability to behave freely on stage, manage their emotional state, and fully express their artistic image during the performance process is one of the important indicators of their professional maturity. In this process, concert activities, open lessons, and creative performances are important pedagogical tools.

In general, improving students' instrumental performance skills depends on the systematic and purposeful use of pedagogical opportunities. Performance classes

organized in accordance with the requirements of modern education serve to develop students' musical thinking, creative independence, and professional competence, and create the basis for their formation as future qualified music specialists.

Analytical discussion.

In the process of analyzing the issue of improving students' instrumental performance skills, it becomes clear that the effectiveness of this activity depends on many pedagogical, psychological, and methodological factors. First of all, the development of performing skills is not limited to the student's technical preparation, but is inextricably linked to his musical thinking, aesthetic taste and emotional experience. Therefore, ensuring the harmony of these factors in the educational process is considered an important pedagogical task. The analysis shows that traditional teaching methods often do not allow the student to fully demonstrate his creative activity. The organization of the performance process solely on the basis of repeated exercises limits the student's independent thinking and musical decision-making skills. On the contrary, modern pedagogical approaches - person-oriented, competency-based and reflective educational models - strengthen the student's role as an active subject in the performance process. The effectiveness of interactive methods in the discussion process deserves special attention. Analyzing musical works, comparing performance options and discussing the artistic image deepen the student's musical thinking. This approach serves to consciously develop performance skills, ensuring the harmony of technical mastery and artistic expression. Especially in the process of collective performance, students learn to listen to each other, coordinate, and feel musical responsibility.

Analytical, the pedagogical significance of independent performing activities is also highly appreciated. In the process of independent training, the student develops the skills to work on himself, identify errors in performance and look for ways to eliminate them. However, the effectiveness of independent activity is closely related to pedagogical guidance and methodological guidance. Otherwise, there is a risk of strengthening incorrectly formed performing skills. Also, pedagogical experiences related to stage practice show that students' performing skills are often fully manifested in a stage setting. The excitement on stage, communication with the audience and the lively expression of an artistic image test the student's emotional stability and performing culture. Therefore, the systematic inclusion of concert activities and open performance classes in the educational process is considered one of the important pedagogical conditions.

Conclusion.

In general, the results of the analytical discussion show that improving students'

musical performance skills should be organized not only as a set of methods, but as a holistic pedagogical system. In this system, the individual characteristics of the student, his creative potential and professional development needs occupy a central place. Only such an approach will allow achieving high results in music education and training competitive, creative specialists.

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